

MODERN METHODS OF EDUCATING YOUNG PEOPLE IN THE SPIRIT OF PATRIOTISM IN THE PROCESS OF SPIRITUAL GROWTH

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Abstract: In the article, the theoretical and methodological foundations of the socio-philosophical research of the phenomenon of youth patriotism in the process of spiritual growth of New Uzbekistan, the priority tasks of education of patriotism in young people in the process of spiritual growth of New Uzbekistan are studied. Also, modern methods of educating young people in the spirit of patriotism in the process of spiritual growth were analyzed.

Key words: New Uzbekistan, scientific-methodological basis, socio-philosophical, phenomenon, spiritual growth, patriotism, modernity, historical-philosophical basis, objectivity, historicity, systematicity, analysis, synthesis, induction-deduction.

INTRODUCTION In today's era of globalization, the views of high morality have somewhat materialized. Now knowledge about the real world and activity in human society has become the main criterion. Today, more than ever, educating young people in the spirit of patriotism is a very exciting, complex and responsible task. In this case, protecting the Motherland, putting the interests of the Motherland above all else, showing dedication to the development of the Motherland, and serving the Motherland should become an important moral criterion and an honorable duty of a citizen.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. The processes of spiritual growth in Uzbekistan are promoted on the basis of the principle of "From national revival to national growth", conceptual ideas in the works, speeches, articles and selective meetings of the President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev, as well as the philosophical heritage of the East and the West. serves as a scientific-methodological basis for this research.

A number of studies have been carried out that include the problems related to clarifying the importance of the processes of spiritual growth in the new stage of development of Uzbekistan. S. Shermuhammedov, A. Saidov, B. Toraev, J. Yakhshilikov, N. Joraev, Q. Nazarov, S. Otamurodov, S. Karimov, A. Kholbekov, R. Jumaev, B. Karimov, T. Our scientists, such as Joraev, I. Ergashev, S. Joraev, M. Kyrgyzboev, A. Erkaev, M. Bekmurodov, V. Kochkarov, M. Jakbarov, A. Muminov, have conducted various researches on the development of the social sphere in society. carried out. Scientists such as R. Ubaidullaeva, Kh.

Abdusattorova have conducted research on the importance of the innovative factor in the new era of social development.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. Today, people live in the era of globalization, where information exchange is accelerating and constantly updating. The process of globalization, together with the development of science and technology, has a significant impact on human spirituality. These processes make the wider formation of the virtue of patriotism in Uzbekistan a social necessity. The reasons for this largely depend on the following factors:

1. The central position of Uzbekistan in the Central Asian region and the fact that the future fate of the region largely depends on Uzbekistan. Whatever path the people of Uzbekistan choose, there is a possibility that the neighbors will follow the same path. Relations in this political space place a special responsibility on strengthening the sense of patriotism.

2. Today, the situation in the region of Central Asia and the Middle East is becoming more complicated. Current tasks indicate the need to improve work on strengthening the sense of patriotism among young people, not to sit indifferently on the development of these events.

3. If the society and the system cannot protect itself in the current dangerous times, it is impossible to achieve a good result in both domestic and foreign policy. The consistent conduct of domestic and foreign policy in Uzbekistan requires the establishment of a system of effective use of modern methods of forming patriotism among young people.

4. The path of spiritual renewal requires that a person be guaranteed a free choice of his political, economic and social lifestyle. This, in turn, violates the rule of humanity and patriotism that everyone born in Uzbekistan, living and working on its land, regardless of nationality and faith, deserves to be a citizen of our republic with equal rights. determines the need to release.

Our enlightened ancestor Alikhontora Soguny said: "Just as it is obligatory for everyone to study religious science, it is also obligatory to learn modern science in order to save the Motherland and the nation. ... For this reason, the boys and girls of our Motherland should understand the basics of every modern science and try to learn it as much as possible, more than others. Because, while fulfilling the words of the wise fathers: "Work is what you know, sword is what you hit", surely the people of the Motherland, especially our modern educated sons and daughters, will do their work and take their rightful places. can have."

In order to understand patriotism and strive for it, it is necessary to acquire certain knowledge and acquire patriotic education. This process

requires the study and analysis of the following situations:

Firstly, at the present time, patriotism and scientific issues related to it are analyzed in a general direction in educational institutions. However, social-spiritual, educational-ethical and political-legal aspects of patriotism are not a separate section of the relevant science, but are interpreted as a small topic of it. This indicates that it is necessary to further improve the educational foundations of instilling a sense of patriotism in the minds of young people, and systematically organize propaganda work. The solution to this complex issue will be achieved first of all through the mutual cooperation of social and humanitarian sciences, interpretation of the theme of patriotism, sense of country in them based on the principle of continuity and consistency, and teaching with the idea of patriotism embedded in the content of these sciences.

Secondly, the task of military lyceums and schools in educating young people in the spirit of patriotism is not only to familiarize them with modern military equipment, to instill the skills of using combat equipment and weapons, to constantly engage in physical education, to teach them to march in ranks, to teach them the unique characteristics of military service. teaching tactics, instilling love for military troops and the military profession, as well as being humble, honest, disciplined, studying, working, setting an example in life, conscientiously studying military service, only good, to study with excellent grades and most importantly to educate a patriot loyal to the country, to be resilient and tenacious, to overcome any difficulties and help comrades in the most difficult time, to follow the orders of the chief and commanders without words consists of teaching.

Thirdly, the main goal of the reforms implemented in our country is that today's generation should use the opportunities given by independence for specific purposes, imagine their dreams and aspirations in harmony with their noble feelings such as the prosperity of the Motherland, connect their destiny with the destiny of this Motherland. implies the necessity of reaching a personal agreement. Therefore, in the current era of globalization, thinking more deeply about the objective conditions for the formation of true patriotism based on high humanity among young people is one of the tactical and strategic goals of spiritual processes.

Fourthly, after our country gained its independence, the state system also changed, and important programs were implemented in this regard. However, this change was formed based on the creation of a unique "Uzbek model" and not due to direct assimilation of the experience and traditions of some countries.

Now, every person who considers himself a member of this society, who is not indifferent to the fate of the people, the fate of the country, must define his position as a citizen and his views.

Fifth, in school education, the lessons of preparing young people for military service before the draft have become an important direction of educating the modern generation in the spirit of patriotism. In this regard, it is possible to point out that military education has been launched in the educational institutions of our republic, and the activities of educational institutions aimed at training military personnel. In particular, the facilities created for high-level training and sports in vocational colleges, the purposeful organization of the lesson for the preparation of young people for military service before the students are called up based on a special program, the classrooms have visual aids that reflect the power of the Armed Forces of our country, modern military weapons are equipped with training copies, literature, computers and electronic textbooks, the basics of military work, the rules of marching, marksmanship, movement in emergency situations, etc., arouse interest in patriotic education among young patriots.

Today, large-scale work has been carried out to establish the Armed Forces that meet the requirements of the time and world standards, to ensure the independence, security and territorial integrity of our country, and to form the national army. In the end, this served as a basis for further strengthening of our peace and defense power of our country.

In fact, the current globalization process requires the effective use of traditional and modern methods of formation of patriotism among young people. These are the following methods.

1. Propaganda method. The educational-ethical content of patriotism and the scientific-theoretical basis of these processes being carried out in our country, and their new aspects are to be revealed perfectly. Therefore, it is necessary to explain the sense of patriotism to young people in a simple and concise way and to turn them into active and enthusiastic participants in the construction of a society that meets the requirements of the new life and times.

2. Community method. Today, the general combat readiness of our Armed Forces is determined by the level of combat readiness of units, formations, parts and divisions. Military units represent a strictly defined social group that operates according to its internal structure, general obligations of military personnel and service relations between them, rules of internal order, duties of officials, daily and domestic conditions, deployment of military personnel. , the

issues of conducting internal service are strictly defined in the main cases of Discipline and Internal Service Regulations. According to military researcher YE. Volkov: "The implementation of social relations within the framework of the Armed Forces on the basis of a strict order, increasing the probability of deviant behavior, is one of the objective reasons for the existence of deviant behavior in the army."

3. Traditional method. Military tradition is a historically formed, generation-to-generation idea, rule, tradition, and behavior related to the military service process in the army, the performance of combat tasks, the training of personnel, and the daily life of military personnel. appears in the standards. The system of military traditions in the Armed Forces includes three main areas of military activity - Combat traditions, Military life traditions and Educational traditions. This opinion is confirmed by the military researcher E. Rasulev that "Traditions are not only a standard of behavior, but also a means of reflecting the essence of socially significant events in military service, a form of military thinking."

4. Value priority method. It is impossible to form a sense of patriotism in military personnel without developing human qualities such as loyalty to national values, advanced traditions, moral principles, and high culture. Because, if you look at the new development path of Uzbekistan, you can see that a large-scale work has been done to realize patriotism and raise a brave and courageous generation. The main goal of the civil society being established in Uzbekistan is to form a generation that is not indifferent to the development of the Motherland, the peace of the country, and the well-being of the people. In this, national and universal values serve as a pragmatic basis.

5. Method of modernity. Difficulties, obstacles, imbalances, even the increase of criminal activities during the transition period cannot extinguish the feeling of the Motherland in the heart of a person of pure conscience, if it has become a deep belief. As long as there are social groups with diverse goals and interests, different and sometimes contradictory perceptions of the common goal will remain. There has never been an absolutely ideal state or system anywhere. The birth of new generations brings new problems to the society; it is this continuity and gradualness that ensures the continuous and gradual continuation of social life. Therefore, with the formation of a sense of patriotism in the transitional generations, the tasks in this regard are not fully fulfilled, but it is a foundation for new tasks at a new stage.

CONCLUSION. In conclusion, the conceptual foundations of strengthening patriotism in young people are related to the formation of social and moral qualities such as national thinking, moral courage, a firm civic position, a sense of courage, and living with clear and noble goals. The patriotism, which requires regular implementation based on a large-scale, systematic and purposeful plan, covers functional and organizational aspects. The moral basis of these aspects is the unity of education and upbringing and the dialectic unity between culture - spirituality - philosophy.

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